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Construction of the XLS Accelerating Structure Pre-Prototype

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ABSTRACT

This following document (D7.5) confirms the successful construction of the CompactLight accelerating structure prototype within the I.FAST WP7. This achievement marks a key step towards Deliverable D7.6 and the realization of the full accelerating structure.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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1 Introduction

This report describes the X-band accelerating structure designed for the CompactLight project (<https://www.compactlight.eu/>), detailing the construction phases of the first prototype of the structure. The work has been carried out for the I.FAST work package 7.

CompactLight was a Design Study funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, completed in 2021 with the design of an innovative, compact, and cost-effective hard X-ray FEL facility, using the most advanced technologies developed for accelerator components, in terms of high brightness photo-injectors, compact and very high-gradient X-band accelerating structures, as well as state-of-the-art undulators.

The CompactLight linac consists of approximately one hundred 0.9m long X-band accelerating structures that can operate both in a high-gradient mode, at 65 MV/m and 100 Hz pulse repetition rate, and high-repetition rate mode, at 30 MV/m and 1 kHz pulse repetition rate. The structure parameters have been optimized for both radio frequency and beam dynamics performance and have higher order transverse mode suppression for stable two-bunch operation. The cooling circuit has been designed to accommodate the high average power of the high-repetition rate mode and optimized for minimum difference between operating modes. Finally, the mechanical design of the structures has also been analyzed and optimized for industrial production.

2 RF design of the CompactLight accelerating structure

The design and optimization of a linear accelerator based on traveling-wave structures involve several critical steps [1]. These steps are outlined below:

- 1. Selection of a Reference Accelerating Field**
Begin by establishing a reference value for the accelerating field, which serves as a baseline for subsequent design choices.
- 2. Definition of RF Power Sources and Pulse Compressor Characteristics**
Specify the characteristics of the RF power sources and, if applicable, the pulse compression system to ensure compatibility with the desired performance parameters.
- 3. Determination of the Average Iris Radius**
Set the average iris radius of the accelerating structure according to the requirements of beam dynamics.
- 4. Electromagnetic Design of the Regular Cells**
Conduct the electromagnetic design and optimization of regular cells, which form the core of the accelerating structure.
- 5. Optimization of Structure Length and Iris Tapering**
Explore variations in the total length of the structure and the tapering of the iris to maximize the effective shunt impedance. This step aims to enhance efficiency and reduce the total number of RF power sources needed.

6. Validation Against Breakdown Rate Predictors

Assess breakdown rate predictors, including the modified Poynting vector, surface electric field, and pulsed heating, to ensure they remain within acceptable limits at the nominal operating gradient.

7. Wakefield Simulations

Perform wakefield simulations to evaluate beam break-up effects and confirm the stability of the particle beam under operating conditions.

8. Final Electromagnetic Design of the Structure

Refine the electromagnetic design to incorporate input and output couplers, ensuring that breakdown predictors such as pulsed heating are maintained at acceptable levels.

9. Design of a Realistic RF Module

Develop a detailed RF module design, including the power distribution network, to enable efficient operation of the structure.

The design process typically involves several iterations of these steps to achieve an optimal balance between performance, efficiency, and reliability. The following paragraphs outline the key steps involved in the design process.

2.1 DESIGN OF THE REGULAR CELL

The design of the regular cell was developed using the ANSYS Electronic desktop simulation tool, that is a Finite Element Method (FEM) solver for analyzing electromagnetic structures. Figure 1 illustrates a sketch of the cell geometry.

Figure 1: Sketch of the single cell with main parametrized dimensions.

In the figure, a represents the iris radius, b is the outer radius, t denotes the iris thickness, r_0 is the rounding radius of the cell, and $r_1 = r_2$ defines the aspect ratio of the iris's elliptical profile. The cell length, d , is calculated based on an operating frequency of 11.994,2 MHz and a cell phase advance of $2\pi/3$, resulting in 8.332 mm.

The design process focused on minimizing the modified Poynting vector, normalized to the average accelerating gradient Sc_{max}/E_{acc}^2 while maximizing RF efficiency. RF efficiency was evaluated

using the shunt impedance per unit length (R) parameter. An elliptical shape for the irises was adopted to reduce the peak modified Poynting vector on the surface. It was determined that setting $r_1/r_2 = 1.3$ provides an optimal balance between high-gradient performance and efficiency. Additionally, the rounding radius r_0 was set to 2.5 mm. After defining the iris shape, the primary cell parameters (shunt impedance per unit length (R), quality factor (Q), group velocity (v_g), and normalized modified Poynting vector (Sc_{max}/E_{acc}^2), were calculated as functions of the iris radius (a) and iris thickness (t), as reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Main RF and geometrical parameters as a function of the iris radius and the iris thickness.

The values of a were varied between 2 mm and 5 mm, while t ranged from 1.5 mm to 2.25 mm. Based on these calculations, the design of the accelerating structures was finalized. The data in Fig. 2 were subsequently smoothed using MATLAB's built-in interpolator, with a mesh spacing of 1 mm for both a and t . The results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Main RF and geometrical parameters as a function of the iris radius and the iris thickness after interpolation with MATLAB.

2.2 ANALYTICAL STRUCTURE LENGTH OPTIMIZATION

With the average iris radius of the structure defined, the first step in designing the entire structure was to identify the optimal lengths for both Constant Impedance (CI) and Constant Gradient (CG) structures. This process also involved simulating the RF pulse compressor, utilizing the formulas for the SLED pulse compression system [3] applicable to both CI and CG structures [4, 5], implemented through MATLAB code [6, 7].

The effective shunt impedance, as a function of the accelerating structure attenuation, is shown in Fig. 5 for both CI and CG structures, while the optimal structure length as a function of the average iris aperture is depicted in Figure 6. For the CI structure, the optimal length has been fixed at 0.890 m, and for the CG structure, 0.818 m. These values served as the basis for a numerical optimization of iris tapering, as described in the following section.

Figure 5: Effective shunt impedance as a function of the section attenuation for CI and CG structures.

Figure 6: Optimal structure length as function of the average iris radius for CI and CG structures.

2.3 IRIS TAPERING

Two-bunch operation in CompactLight is essential for pump-and-probe experiments. However, this operational mode introduces a critical design challenge: addressing the long-range transverse wakefield behavior of the accelerating structure. The wakefield excited by the leading bunch can influence the trajectory of the trailing bunch, leading to emittance growth. To mitigate this, long-range transverse wakefield suppression is necessary. This suppression can be achieved by varying the iris diameter along the structure's length, which detunes the synchronous frequencies of the most significant transverse modes. This detuning induces decoherence in the transverse wakefield, reducing its amplitude [11–15].

The initial constant gradient (CG) design of the X-band RF structure featured a linear tapering of the iris aperture, from 4.278 mm to 2.722 mm, with a constant iris thickness of 2 mm. The long-range transverse wakefield of this design was calculated using GdfidL [16], as shown in Fig. 7. With linear iris tapering, the long-range transverse wakefield at the 4th, 6th, and 10th RF cycles was found to be 120, 45.83, and 18.8 V/pC/mm/m, respectively. To further suppress the wakefield, a Gaussian-like aperture tapering combined with a linear tapering of iris thickness was proposed. Through a multi-

parameter optimization of the tapering parameters, the final iris aperture and thickness profiles were determined, as illustrated in Figure 8. The blue line represents the dimensions of the linear iris design, while the red line shows the Gaussian-like design.

The long-range transverse wakefield for the Gaussian-like iris design is presented in Fig. 9. The wakefield of the linear iris design (blue line) is compared to the Gaussian-like design (red line). The optimal compromise between fundamental-mode performance and minimum bunch spacing was achieved with a spacing of the 10th RF cycle. In this configuration, the wakefield experienced by the second bunch is reduced to 3.65 V/pC/mm/m. Moreover, the wakefield envelope of the Gaussian-like design at the 10th RF cycle is smaller than that of the linear iris design, ensuring more stable and robust operation.

Figure 7: Long-range transverse wakefield of the initial linear iris design.

Figure 8: The iris dimension of the RF structure. Left figure is the distribution of the iris aperture.

Right figure is the distribution of the iris thickness.

Figure 9: Long-range transverse wakefields of the initial design and the gaussian-like iris design.

2.4 INPUT AND OUTPUT RF POWER COUPLERS

Magnetically coupled input and output power couplers were chosen for their compact design. Key design considerations for these couplers include achieving impedance matching, minimizing peak surface electric fields, and reducing the quadrupolar component of the accelerating field within the structure. Critical geometric parameters for the design are the radii r_1 and r_2 , which correspond to the roundings between the waveguide and the slot, and between the slot and the matching cell, respectively. These radii define a geometry known as z-coupling (Figure 10).

Increasing the curvature of the coupler slot reduces the surface magnetic field, thereby mitigating pulsed heating. For both the input and output couplers, r_2 is fixed at 4 mm, while r_1 is set to 2 mm.

Figure 10: Detail of the RF power coupler with the main parameters.

To minimize the quadrupolar component of the magnetic field, a racetrack geometry has been incorporated into the design. Δx represents the distance between the center of the coupler and the centers of the semicircles with radius R_c . Table 1 summarizes the key geometrical parameters for both the input and output couplers. A parameter scan of the coupler dimensions determined that the reflection coefficient at the input port is -44.9 dB for the input coupler and -37 dB for the output coupler. Additionally, the input coupler exhibits a pulsed heating of 24°C, which is deemed entirely safe for high-field operations.

Figure 11 presents a comparison between couplers with and without a racetrack geometry. Results are referenced to a 2 mm radius arc at the longitudinal center of the coupler. The racetrack geometry effectively minimizes the quadrupolar component of the magnetic field. With this geometry, the integrated equivalent quadrupole gradient is reduced to 4 mT, compared to 30 mT without the racetrack.

Table 1: Main geometrical parameters of the RF power couplers of the X-band accelerating structures.

Parameter	Units	Input coupler	Output coupler
Waveguide rounding r_{wg}	mm	2	
Waveguide-slot rounding r_1	mm	2	
Slot-matching cell rounding r_2	mm	4	
Matching cell radius R_c	mm	5.063	6.308
Off-axis circle center Δx	mm	8.359	4.765
Slot width w	mm	9.017	7.819

Figure 11: Magnitude of the magnetic field in the center of the matching cell in input (left) and output (right) coupler with and without the racetrack (circle radius r of 2 mm).

2.5 RF STRUCTURE PARAMETERS

Table 2 lists the main parameters of the structures that can operate both in a high-gradient mode, at 65 MV/m and 100 Hz pulse repetition rate, and high-repetition rate mode, at 30 MV/m and 1 kHz pulse repetition rate. and the RF module.

Table 2: Main parameters of the RF structures and modules

Parameter	Units	Value		
Frequency	GHz	11.994		
Peak Klystron power (100-250 Hz)	MW	50		
Peak klystron power (1kHz)	MW	10		
RF pulse length (250 Hz)	μs	1.5 (0.15)		
Waveguide power attenuation	%	≈ 10		
Average iris radius $\langle a \rangle$	mm	3.5		
Iris radius a	mm	4.3-2.7		
Iris thickness t	mm	2-2.24		
Structure length L_s	m	0.9		
Unloaded SLED Q-factor Q_0		18000		
External SLED Q-factor Q_{ext}		23300		
Shunt impedance R	$M\Omega/m$	85-111		
Peak modified Poynting vector	$W/\mu m^2$	3.4		
Group velocity v_g/c	%	4.7-0.9		
Filling time t_f	ns	146		
Repetition rate	Hz	100	250	10000
Pulse compressor		ON	OFF	ON
Required klystron power	MW	44	44	9
Average accelerating gradient	MV/m	65	30	30

The gradient profile along the structure (after one filling time) is shown in Figure 12, while the power distribution (averaged over the pulse length and normalized to the peak value) is illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Accelerating gradient profile along the structure after one filling time.

Figure 13: Power distribution (averaged over the pulse length and normalized to the peak value).

3 Mechanical design and thermal stabilization

In the previous project Compact*Light (XLS), the design choices and concept design was described in deliverable Del4.3; Accelerating structure design and fabrication procedure. In this project the design iteration from the RF to the detailed design and mechanical drawings was redone with the latest insight and numbers, see figure 14

Figure 14. Design flow

The choices for both mechanical and cooling design were briefly revisited. The asymmetric cool channel geometry due to the output coupler geometry, remains a distinctive feature, see Figure 15. The thermo-mechanical FEM calculations and the manufacturing of the first structure are described below.

Figure 15. Single disk geometry, with the asymmetric cooling channels and the brazing channels around the iris and at the outer rim.

3.1 COOLING GEOMETRY AND THERMAL STABILITY

From the newest calculated RF dimensions, thermo-mechanical FEM calculations were done to determine the temperature at the iris and the corresponding deformations for disc 2, 54 and 106.

Based on thermo-mechanical analyses of X-band cavities made by M. van den Berg, 4 cooling channels of 6 mm with a water flow of 3 l/min was chosen. The cooling channels are connected at the back of the structure, so 2 input and 2 output water lines are needed in the front, see Figure 16. This will lead to a water pressure of around $6 \cdot 10^5$ Pa needed at the accelerator structure, this pressure on the water channels is taken into account in the deformation calculations.

Figure 16. Cooling channel routing

Two load cases are calculated for the 3 disks; both the low and high power heat load cases (100 Hz repetition rate; 1 kW dissipation and 1000 Hz repetition rate; 2.2 kW dissipation). To get the deformation in both cases as similar as possible, the water temperature in the low rep rate case is raised around 4.5 degrees Celsius, to match the temperature in the irises.

There is a tradeoff to be made, as the temperature profile over the structure is different for the low rep rate case and the high rep rate case. With the lower heat load (and the higher water temperature) the iris temperature of disk 2 will be slightly higher, disk 54 will be slightly lower and will be around the same for disk 106.

In **Error! Reference source not found.** a typical temperature result is shown, in this case for disk 2 for the high rep rate, with a cooling water temperature of 30 degrees Celsius. The corresponding total deformation (including water pressure) is shown on the right.

Figure 17. Left: temperature result of disk 2 in the high heat load case. Right: the corresponding total deformation.

With these results, the parameters from the RF are recalculated and adjusted, to compensate for the difference in deformation. After that, another iteration was done to compensate for the manufacturing process, which is done at a room temperature of 20 degrees. This is just a constant, calculated with difference in the foreseen operating temperature and the manufacturing temperature times the expansion coefficient of the copper.

The 3D model of the structure is shown below, Figure 18.

Figure 18. 3D model of the structure

From this the detailed mechanical drawings are made, see Figure 19. Detailed discs drawing (drawing number: 131-92371)

Figure 19. Detailed discs drawing (2 sheets)

3.2 MANUFACTURING PROCESS

In this section the route towards the production of the individual accelerator parts is described. The intent is to give general overview of the typical work-flow.

The typical work-flow of high precision mono-parts are reported below:

1. Production of starting material
2. Pre-machining
3. Thermal annealing
4. Final-machining
5. Metrology
6. Cleaning
7. Packaging

A description of the work-flow steps are reported in the following paragraphs.

3.2.1 Production of starting-material:

As first step of the production work-flow is the production of the starting-material. The starting material is defined as Oxygen free copper (Cu-OFE). This step is cutting the raw material (typically bar stock) into individual blanks.

3.2.2 Pre-machining:

The bulk material of the blanks is removed during the pre-machining step, by so called high-precision machines, with a high reproducibility. The machining of the material has to be done such that the amount of stress introduced in the material is low and especially reproducible. All not critical dimensions of the parts are made in this production step. All critical dimensions and low roughness surfaces, such as the "iris" of the discs, will still have additional material, which will be removed in later productions steps.

All non-critical features, such as brazing grooves and thermal holes, will also be made in this production step.

Figure 20 is a picture of a pre-machined disc.

Figure 20. Pre-machined disc

3.2.3 Thermal annealing:

After pre-machining, there will be some stress in the material that needs to be relieved before final machining. This stress can cause deformation of the parts during brazing techniques due to elevated temperature.

The annealing process not only releases stress in the material, it also changes the material on a microscope level i.e. the grain-size and its distribution is also affected by the annealing process.

Experiences in past learn that a single annealing step at 240 °C yields the best combined result in stress relief and grain dimensions.

3.2.4 Final-machining:

The final machining consists of alternating machining and measurements steps, in order to assure product quality. Furthermore, the cleanliness of the parts is of high importance as contamination of the parts will lead to contamination of the vacuum-system where they are used in.

The final machining is preformed on extremely high-precision machines. And the cutting tools are so-called single point diamond tools allow to machine the soft oxygen free copper with a high accuracy combined with a mirror finished surface. See Figure 21.

Figure 21. Membrane box

The machining steps are executed in two separated in two distinct groups i.e. milling and turning. In a milling operation, the machine tool rotates and removes material in an intermittent behaviour i.e. each revolution of the tool a small chip of material is removed. In a turning operation, the part rotates and the machine tool remains in contact with the part and a continuous ribbon-like stream of material is removed. Due to this difference in nature a turning surface results in a lower surface roughness compared to a milled surface.

3.2.5 Metrology:

During and after machining parts need to be measured to ensure that the final parts are within specifications. Depending on the stability of the process the interval at which parts are to be measured can vary from 100% for critical dimensions to 1-in-4 of even 1-in-8 depending for less critical dimensions.

Form and position tolerances are measured with a touch probe of a Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM). Measuring forces need to be much lower than normally can be expected on the CMM as no metrology marks can be left on the surface.

3.2.6 Cleaning:

The Parts have to be ultra clean and this to be kept in mind during the entire manufacturing process. To avoid all possible scratches on the parts gloves need to be worn during the pre- and end-machining. Cutting fluids need to be free of chlorine or sulphur as this can contaminate the parts, resulting in effecting the RF function. Cutting fluids, used in the process, need to be removed with an ultrasonic cleaning method. Followed by a vapor degreasing step. Given the very fragile parts special holding tools need to be developed and made for the cleaning steps.

3.2.7 Packaging:

Given the fragile nature of the parts i.e. especially the centre zone (Iris) with RF functionality, packaging is a crucial step in shipping the parts to the partner for the next fabrication step. Packaging of the individual discs is done in membrane boxes, see Figure 22.

Figure 22. Membrane box

4 Metrology control

One of the responsibilities from CERN is to ensure the quality of the parts delivered before the assembly process. For doing so, CERN proposed to measure some randomly selected parts to ensure the process followed by VDL ETG Precision was ok.

The machine used for doing that metrology control was the LEITZ PPMC 12, CMM used for the highest accurate measurements at CERN.

Following the drawings mentioned before Figure 6) and establishing a reference system as seen on the Figure 23, all selected parts were measured.

Figure 23. Reference system for metrology

With the aim of optimising the time and resources, a selection on the key assembly features was done. Only 13 reference dimensions were taken into account. (Figure 24)

Figure 24. Dimensions to be measured at CERN

After metrology reports from discs 49, 54, 57, 59, 60, 62, 64, 65, 68, 69 and all waveguides, no significant deviations were observed. Only some deviations on the shape of the iris can be spotted on the report (Figure 25) where we can see minor deviations and after conversations with metrology experts can be explained by a mispositioning of the reference between the original drawing and the CMM machine.

IRIS PROFILES:							
E2_SCAN1_ACNO							
PROFILE Z+							
MAX	0.0011	0.0000	0.0015	-0.0015	0.0011		
MIN	-0.0080	0.0000	0.0015	-0.0015	0.0080		0.0065 ◀
FFORM	0.0161	0.0000	0.0030	0.0000	0.0161		0.0131 ◀
E2_SCAN2_ACNO							
PROFILE X+							
MAX	0.0010	0.0000	0.0015	-0.0015	0.0010		
MIN	-0.0087	0.0000	0.0015	-0.0015	0.0087		0.0072 ◀
FFORM	0.0174	0.0000	0.0030	0.0000	0.0174		0.0144 ◀
E2_SCAN3_ACNO							
PROFILE Z-							
MAX	0.0010	0.0000	0.0015	-0.0015	0.0010		
MIN	-0.0084	0.0000	0.0015	-0.0015	0.0084		0.0069 ◀
FFORM	0.0168	0.0000	0.0030	0.0000	0.0168		0.0138 ◀
E2_SCAN4_ACNO							
PROFILE X-							
MAX	0.0013	0.0000	0.0015	-0.0015	0.0013		
MIN	-0.0081	0.0000	0.0015	-0.0015	0.0081		0.0066 ◀
FFORM	0.0163	0.0000	0.0030	0.0000	0.0163		0.0133 ◀

Figure 25. Dimensions from iris on cell 54 from CERN.

Those results were discussed within the team members and we agreed that that could be a reasonable explanation. Indeed, after checking the metrology reports from VDL ETG (Figure 26) all those values were on the range of 1 micron deviation or bellow that value.

	DIN Lineform on side ref_A.x	5,5600	5,5598			0,0003	
	DIN Lineform on side ref_A.y	0,0000	0,0000			0,0000	
	DIN Lineform on side ref_A.z	-10,3925	-10,3918			-0,0007	
	DIN Lineform opposite ref_A.x	9,1261	9,1273			-0,0012	
	DIN Lineform opposite ref_A.y	0,0000	0,0000			0,0000	
	DIN Lineform opposite ref_A.z	-4,3210	-4,3206			-0,0004	
	DIN Lineform total.x	9,1261	9,1273			-0,0012	
	DIN Lineform total.y	0,0000	0,0000			0,0000	
	DIN Lineform total.z	-4,3210	-4,3206			-0,0004	

Figure 26. Dimensions from iris on cell 54 from VDL ETG.

Respect all the rest of variables, all are within the ranges of tolerances and meets the requirements for a good assembly process and RF performance.

On the waveguide area, the focus was always on the possibility of a good assembly process. Given the fact that the RF volume on that part is not extremely crucial for the correct performance of the accelerating machine, a strong focus was directed to the interface waveguide-accelerating structure.

With that focus in mind a profile of the virtual future assemble (the two parts shaping the waveguide were manually assembled during metrology) was obtained as seen on the Figure 27. The deviation is smaller than it is shown on the figure because most of the deviation is coming from the fact that the assembly is temporal and a bid step is seen just in that area. If we correct that, the possible deviation is just on the negative side, giving us more room for introducing the waveguide into the pocket. The centring of them will be ensured during the brazing procedure.

Figure 27. Profile from waveguide 2 measured at CERN.

5 Brazing procedures

CPI TMD are responsible for the brazing of the XLS accelerating structure. As part of their work, they provided input into the structure design to enable optimal assembly and brazing, they determined the braze type and quantity to be used, and they designed and manufactured the jig required for construction and braze of the prototype structure.

5.1 PROTOTYPE STACK ASSEMBLY PROCEDURE

Prior to undertaking the prototype stack build, two test stacks were built to test the proposed stack assembly procedure and braze material. The test stacks were made up of a small number of test XLS accelerating structure disks (131-92371, Figure 28.), which allowed the test to be as representative of the final prototype structure build as possible.

It is important that all disks in the accelerating structure are aligned to one another, CPI TMD proposed using the four cooling holes in each disk as an alignment feature. CPI TMD designed and manufactured a disk alignment jig, seen in figure 10., which uses precision machined stainless steel pins to align each disk during the stacking process. The assembly procedure proposed is as follows:

1. Load the first disk onto the alignment jig at room temperature, ensuring the braze groove is facing upwards and is accessible.
2. Pre-formed braze material is placed in the two circular braze grooves.
3. A second disk is then placed in a warm air oven set to 75 degrees Celsius and left in the oven until the disk temperature equalises (approximately 1.5 hours).
4. Once the second disk is at 75 degrees Celsius, it is removed from the warm air oven and quickly transferred to the alignment jig. It is loaded onto the jig, using the pins of the jig to align it through the four cooling holes, and it is then moved down the jig until it fits flush with the first disk.
5. Once the disks are joined, a weight (approximately 2 kg) is added on top of the disks to ensure they remain flush as the assembly cools to room temperature.
6. After the assembly has returned to room temperature, steps 2-5 are repeated to stack additional disks.

Figure 28. Test structure assembly jig

CPI TMD calculated the required amount of braze material using the 3D models of the disks provided by VDL. The braze gap volume was determined based upon maximum allowable tolerances and then 40% extra braze material was added on. It was determined that a 1 mm diameter braze wire was sufficient for the larger outer braze groove and a 0.5 mm wire was sufficient for the smaller inner braze groove.

Two test stacks were constructed and brazed using the assembly method stated above. Following this, they were successfully leak checked and then returned to CERN for further analysis. Figures 29 and 30 show some photos from the test stack assembly. It was agreed this assembly process would be acceptable for the full prototype build.

Figure 29. (L) test disks in the warm air oven, (R) three disks stacked on the jig, thermocouple used to measure temperature

Figure 30. (L) weight on top of disk stack during construction, (R) assembly within furnace ready to be brazed

5.2 RF COUPLERS BRAZING TESTS

CPI TMD were responsible for brazing of the waveguide assemblies and the RF couplers. The waveguides were delivered in two parts, the main body and the lid. COMEB had machined a braze groove into the main body on the surface in contact with the lid. CPI TMD proposed brazing the waveguides together by themselves first, then they would be brazed to the waveguide flanges in a different braze process.

Brazing the waveguides without the flanges meant there was no feature to locate the body and the lid to one another. To resolve this, CPI TMD used a flat ceramic on each side of the waveguide assembly to align both parts, weights were then placed against the ceramics to keep them in place. The constructed assembly ready for brazing can be seen in Figure 31.

Figure 31. (L) assembled waveguide assembly, (R) ceramic weights added to the lid for brazing

The braze was successful and some photos of the brazed waveguide assembly can be seen in Figure 32.

Figure 32. Brazed waveguide assembly

COMEB have since updated the design of the waveguides to include screws that screw the lid and the body together, which makes alignment of the two parts easier.

The second braze procedure saw CPI TMD braze both RF couplers together, along with their ConFlat (CF) flanges and cooling pipes. Once again, CPI TMD determined the braze and braze quantity for these brazes, as the braze geometry for the RF couplers differ from the rest of the disks. The waveguides were not brazed to the RF couplers in this braze step, however they were inserted to align the two disks and then removed before brazing. Figure 33 shows the construction process of this second braze step.

Figure 33. (L) constructed RF coupler assembly, waveguide used to alignment, (R) constructed RF coupler assembly ready for braze

Both couplers were brazed simultaneously, Figure 34 shows the constructed couplers within CPI TMD's furnace prior to being brazed.

Figure 34. RF coupler assemblies ready for brazing

Once the RF coupler assemblies were brazed, the third planned braze step added both the waveguides and their flanges to the assembly. To do this, CPI TMD turned the assembly 90 degrees to minimise the risk of misalignment, a measurement tool was used to ensure that the assembly was as level as possible and braze glue was then used to hold the waveguides and their flanges in place while the assembly was transferred to the furnace. Figure 35 shows the constructed assemblies.

Figure 35. (L) constructed RF coupler assemblies, (R) assemblies in CPI TMD's metrology department being measured prior to brazing

This third braze completed the RF coupler assemblies.

5.3 PROBLEMS EXPERIENCED IN BRAZING TESTS

CPI TMD experienced a number of issues in the brazing of the RF coupler assemblies which resulted in them being unsuitable for use once brazed due to them not being ultra-high vacuum (UHV) compatible.

Uncoated stainless steel

CPI TMD do not braze bare stainless steel, as the chromium within stainless steel causes a chromium-oxide layer when the part is left in contact with air. Braze material does not wet well to the oxide layer on stainless steel, therefore CPI TMD recommend that all stainless steel parts, such as the flanges and cooling pipes used in the XLS accelerating structure, are nickel plated with a thickness of between 7-25 microns.

The waveguide flanges provided by CERN were delivered with a nickel plating, although the thickness of the nickel plating was not measured. The CF flanges and cooling pipes delivered by VDL were not nickel plated, however an assumption was made by CPI TMD that all parts were being delivered to them fully machined and ready for brazing, which included an assumption all stainless steel parts were suitably nickel plated.

As a result, when the RF coupler parts were brazed in the second braze step, shown in figure 16, the CF flanges and cooling pipes developed a blue oxide layer on their way up to braze temperature, resulting in the braze material failing to wet properly. This resulted in vacuum leaks and evidence of this issue can be seen in figures 36 and 37.

Figure 36. CF flange and cooling pipes oxidised, turned blue

Figure 37. blue oxidised cooling pipe, no braze fillet between the cooling pipe and the RF coupler disk shows lack of adhesion

In addition to this, the waveguide flanges, which were nickel plated by CERN, also did not adhere well to the braze material. CPI TMD suspects the plating layer may be too thin as there is visual evidence of the plated parts discolouring post-braze, which should not happen if sufficiently nickel plated.

This issue resulted in vacuum leaks and evidence of this issue can be seen in Figure 38.

Figure 38. waveguide flange post-braze showing evidence of discolouration and clear lack of adhesion to braze material

Braze groove too close to RF cavity

The second issue CPI TMD came across during the second braze shown in figure 15. was a number visible hole in the wall of the RF cavity following the braze. This again impacted the UHV compatibility of the assembly, as the hole connected the braze channel to the UHV cavity. The braze channel is a non-UHV section as it requires vent holes to the outside world, evidence of this issue can be seen in Figure 39, with holes appearing in two areas of just one of the RF coupler assemblies. The second RF coupler assembly did not have this issue.

Figure 39. two holes seen post-brazing of the RF couplers connecting the braze channels to the UHV cavity

It appears that the braze material may have eaten into the copper edge, causing this hole. There is visual evidence of braze material on the surface of the RF cavity, showing that it has flown through the hole. CPI TMD have undertaken an investigation into this failure, they are currently unsure as to why the braze material may have eaten into the copper, however they did discover what they believe to be an issue with the design of one of the RF coupler parts.

The two RF coupler assemblies have different braze groove geometries from one another. The braze groove geometry shown in Figure 40. appeared to braze very well, however the RF coupler shown in Figure 41 displayed the issue shown in Figure 39.

Figure 40. successfully brazed RF coupler

Figure 41. unsuccessfully brazed RF coupler

Review of the models and part drawings highlighted that there appears to be no allowable gap between the braze channel in the part shown in Figure 23. and the inner wall of the RF cavity when the parts are put together. A depiction of this issue can be seen in Figure 24. This means that a minor misalignment of the RF coupler disks, which is possible given they are only aligned using the waveguides, which themselves are not an exact fit, can result in the braze channel connecting to the RF cavity, causing a significant vacuum leak.

CPI TMD attempted to fill the holes seen in Figure 21. by applying a braze paste during the third braze process shown in Figure 20. The braze paste looked as though it may have worked visually, but due to the issue of the flanges not sealing as explained earlier in the report, CPI TMD were unable to leak check the assembly.

CPI TMD recommended shortening the braze channel of the RF coupler shown in Figure 23. in future designs, as the length of the channel was significantly more than needed to fill the braze gap.

Out of tolerance parts or braze gap too large

Another issue CPI TMD have had is related to parts being delivered out of tolerance or with a larger than acceptable braze gap. The CF flanges brazed in the first RF coupler braze, seen in Figure 15., had a braze gap larger than the recommended by the braze manufacturer which also will have impacted the ability of the parts to braze successfully.

Following all of the issues described within this section, the first RF coupler brazed parts were deemed to be unusable and unrecoverable within the timeframe of the project. The project team then agreed to use the second prototype parts to re-build the first planned prototype, while re-machining the part shown in Figure 23. to shorten the braze groove length.

5.4 BRAZING TESTS ON NEW RF COUPLERS

Following delivery of new RF coupler parts, CPI TMD began the process of assembling and brazing the new RF coupler assemblies. CPI TMD had agreed to nickel plate all of the stainless steel parts on delivery, to avoid any plating issues.

As they did before, they initially brazed the waveguide bodies and their lids together, this time using the waveguide flange to align the two parts and then screws to hold the parts in place. The waveguides were then removed from the flanges and brazed separately. This braze went well and a good braze seal could be seen visually.

Following their experience from the first RF coupler braze, CPI TMD changed the second assembly step to make the assembly and alignment easier. This time around, the second braze step brazed the RF coupler disks, the CF flanges, the cooling pipes, and additionally the waveguide assemblies all in one step. CPI TMD felt this reduced the risk of misalignment of the waveguides and waveguide flanges to the disks.

An issue arose during assembly where it was discovered that parts of the RF coupler assembly were poorly fitted. CPI TMD undertook metrology on the parts to discover some parts delivered to CPI TMD were out of tolerance and some parts produced by CPI TMD were also out of tolerance. In particular the braze gap between the CF flange and the coupler disk was too large and the cooling pipes were oversized and would not fit in the cooling pipe holes. This was resolved by CPI TMD

machining down the cooling pipes to size and re-machining a new CF flange, causing a small delay to the assembly schedule.

A second issue arose while CPI TMD were performing metrology on the received parts. During metrology, one of the RF coupler disks fell from its granite mount and landed on the granite table surface, falling approximately 3-5 cm. In doing so, it suffered damage to the brazing surface and, following discussion with the project team, it was determined that the part could not be used in its current condition and while re-work may be possible, it was too high risk. Evidence of the damaged part can be seen in Figure 42.

Figure 42. Microscope photo of RF coupler disk damage

VDL had a spare RF coupler disk which was originally scrapped due to a scratch in the surface of the RF cavity, however the project team agreed that it would be best to use this previously scrapped part rather than attempt to fix the damage to the disk seen in Figure 42.

Once re-machining of all parts had concluded and the replacement RF coupler disk was received, the parts were assembled and brazed. Figure 43 shows the parts assembled in the furnace, ready for brazing.

Figure 43. Second RF coupler assemblies in the furnace ready for braze

The first braze step, shown in Figure 43, went very well. The braze visually adhered well to all of the parts, evidence of this can be seen in Figure 44. It was not possible to leak check the assembly at this point, due to the fact that the waveguide flanges were missing, but CPI TMD relied on a good visual assessment of the braze flow to move on to the second braze procedure.

Figure 44. Visual post-braze analysis of first RF coupler braze

The second braze process added the waveguide flanges to the waveguides, the assembly was turned 90 degrees to ensure the flanges were flat against the face of the waveguides. Figure 45 shows the assembly in the furnace pre-braze.

Figure 45. second RF coupler braze in the furnace

The second RF coupler braze also went very well, with the braze visually adhering well to the waveguides and waveguide flanges, evidence of which can be seen in Figure 46. Following this braze, both assemblies were leak checked and were UHV leak tight, and the RF coupler assemblies were considered complete.

Figure 46. brazed waveguide flange

6 First accelerating structure stack assembly

Once the RF coupler assemblies were complete, work began on construction of the full accelerating structure. CPI TMD now have all of the parts to progress with the full build.

6.1 BRAZING OF THE FIRST PROTOTYPE

The plan for the full structure was to build the stack upside down (in relation to its brazing orientation), once fully built it will be rotated securely and loaded into CPI TMD's furnace for the third and final braze step. To do this, a braze jig has been designed and manufactured that will allow secure rotation and lifting of the fully assembled structure.

Figure 47 shows the partially constructed stack (on the left) and the entire structure assembled (on the right).

Figure 47. Partially constructed accelerating structure

The whole structure, with the two new end disk assemblies, was brazed mid of February 2025. Figure 48 shows the entire structure assembled before brazing.

Figure 48. Entire structure before brazing

Prior to running this braze, a test furnace run was performed to ensure that the braze profile chosen would reach the desired brazing temperature. A thermocouple was attached to the centre of the test mass and the results showed that the braze profile was adequate.

Following the braze run, the structure was removed from the furnace and placed into CPI TMD's cleanroom for vacuum leak testing, see Figure 49. The structure was tested using ultra-high vacuum leak checking equipment and was unfortunately shown to have a gross leak.

Figure 49. RF structure after brazing

CPI TMD attempted to pinpoint the source of the leak, but the structure appeared to be leaking from several sources, and the size of the leak was too large to be able to accurately identify the sources.

In addition, mechanical damage was noted on the outside of the RF coupler, probably due to the thermal expansion of the structure into its braze jig during the brazing cycle, see Figure 50.

Figure 50. Mechanical damage outside the RF coupler of the structure

Prior to furnace, CPI TMD had put the brazing jig through a wet hydrogen greening process, which forms a green oxide layer on the stainless steel. This green oxide layer is applied to prevent the brazing parts from sticking to the braze jig. In addition to this, the braze jig was loosened once the structure was positioned in the furnace, to allow room for thermal expansion of the copper structure.

Despite this, copper did stick to the stainless steel braze jig and expanded into it, causing damage to at least the outside of the stack.

Following preliminary tests at CPI TMD, at the beginning of April 2025 the structure has been sent to CERN for low level RF measurements, mechanical tests (to assess any damage on the RF couplers) and for further evaluation to identify the cause of the vacuum leaks.

In particular CERN Metrology will check the alignment of the structure and, using an endoscope, will also check the brazing alloy penetration on the beam axis of the structure.

In addition, in order to identify the sources of vacuum leaks, the vent holes of the brazing channel will be sealed.

Finally, if necessary, to fully understand the cause of the vacuum leaks, the section will be cut and the brazed areas are analysed.

6.2 METROLOGY AND VACUUM TESTS

Below the metrology report carried out at CERN to verify the alignment of the structure (the full report is in Annex 1).

	MÉTROLOGIE EN-MME-MM RAPPORT DE CONTRÔLE	
EDMS Job Client Contrôleur Machine Précision des mesures Température	3317020 3101080 GONZALEZ Sergio DEQUIDT Mike ZEISS Prismo Ultra 12-18-10 1,2 µm + L/500mm 20°C ±1°C	Date de la mesure 03/07/2025 15:53 N° de plan 134-75071 Désignation IFAST XBAND ASSY Fournisseur N° de pièce 135-00882-002-2 Valeurs rouges ● 203

Figure 51a, shows the structure under measurement with the reference axes.

Measurements taken:

1. The diameters of all the cells in the structure (102 in total), evaluating their deviations from the nominal values. Fig. 51b shows the measured values for the first 10 cells.
2. The value of a reference location for each cell in the structure (102 in total), evaluating all deviations from the nominal values. Fig. 51c shows the measured values for the first 10 cells.
3. The structure axe, assessing any deviations in X^+ , X^- , Y^+ , Y^- , see Fig. 52

All the values shown in Figure 51 and Figure 52 are in mm.

Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
∅ Diamètre1(1)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(2)	80,0120	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0120	0,0100
∅ Diamètre1(3)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(4)	80,0112	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0112	0,0092
∅ Diamètre1(5)	80,0092	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0092	0,0072
∅ Diamètre1(6)	80,0113	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0113	0,0093
∅ Diamètre1(7)	80,0146	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0146	0,0126
∅ Diamètre1(8)	80,0125	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0125	0,0105
∅ Diamètre1(9)	80,0093	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0093	0,0073
∅ Diamètre1(10)	80,0100	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0100	0,0080

b)

Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
⊕ Localisation1(1)	0,0302	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0302	
⊕ Localisation1(2)	0,0219	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0219	
⊕ Localisation1(3)	0,0647	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0647	0,0147
⊕ Localisation1(4)	0,0888	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0888	0,0388
⊕ Localisation1(5)	0,1152	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1152	0,0652
⊕ Localisation1(6)	0,1377	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1377	0,0877
⊕ Localisation1(7)	0,1589	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1589	0,1089
⊕ Localisation1(8)	0,1807	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1807	0,1307
⊕ Localisation1(9)	0,2010	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2010	0,1510
⊕ Localisation1(10)	0,2172	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2172	0,1672

Figure 51. a) Accelerating structure with coordinate system under measurement

b) Measurement of the diameter of the first ten cells of the structure

c) Reference point measurements of the first ten cells of the structure

Figure 52. Structure axis measurements (on the left) and X^+ , X^- , Y^+ , Y^- deviations (table on the right)

Summarizing 203 measurement points are out of tolerance, with deviations of up to 1.25 mm. The axis of the structure has a clear “banana shape”, with a maximum deviation in the middle of up to 0.42 mm, almost 100 times higher than expected, that make the structure use rather problematic!

We are analysing the issues that led to these unacceptable results. These are probably due to the method used to assembly the whole cell stack, the structure rotation before brazing, or an inadequate compensation for copper expansion during brazing. As already reported, the copper stick to the stainless steel braze jig and expanded into it during brazing.

All these issues will need to be addressed and corrected before the assembling and brazing of the second structure.

6.3 LOW LEVEL RF MEASUREMENTS AND RF CHARACTERIZATION

Following the mechanical measurements, the structure was measured and characterized on a microwave bench (see Figure 53 below).

Figure 53. Structure RF measurements

A 110 GHz, continuous sweep, Rodhe & Schwarz vector network analyzer (VNA), with a four-port calibration, has been used, using the following configuration:

- Center frequency 11.994 GHz
- 300 MHz span
- No. of points 10001
- IF bandwidth 1kHz

The structure was characterised by measuring the S parameters in reflection (S_{11} , S_{22}), see Figure 54, and transmission (S_{12} , S_{21}), see Figure 55, representing the magnitude and phase of RF reflected and transmitted. The values shown in the graphs include the air correction.

Figure 54. Structure input and output S parameters (in reflection)

Figure 55. Structure input and output S parameters (in transmission)

The measured parameters are quite acceptable. Although the structure has a slightly high insertion loss, (≈ 10 dB), it is quite well matched with a return loss >20 dB.

At this stage, it was not possible to perform the bead-pull test, to measure the electric field distribution within the accelerating structure, as its overall length, including the input-output RF couplers, exceeds one metre and the available bead-pull system was limited to one. We plan to modify the system and repeat the RF tests, including the RF field distribution.

7 Conclusions

The first part of the project for the construction of the CompactLight accelerating structure has been completed. The pre-prototype was built in several stages. While some stages went smoothly, without particular problems, others encountered severe technical issues.

In particular:

- We have not experienced any particular problems with the RF design and the development of the engineering drawings of the structure.
- The precision machining of all the elementary cells were successful.
- Most of the brazing tests, carried out on a reduced number of cells (3-5), went well.

Conversely, the activities that proved to be somewhat problematic were:

- The stacking of cells and assembly of the entire structure, as well as the braze jig, used for secure rotation and lifting of the fully assembled structure prior to brazing, proved to be quite problematic.
- The brazing process, the instability of the oven temperature, and the inadequate compensation for copper expansion inside the jig during the brazing cycle, have all been problematic and have certainly contributed to the mechanical and vacuum issues encountered with the brazed structure.

For these reasons, it is crucial to identify the causes of the problems encountered in order to make the necessary changes to the brazing process for the second accelerating structure.

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9 Annexe

ANNEXE 1

CERN METROLOGY REPORT

**MÉTROLOGIE EN-MME-MM
RAPPORT DE CONTRÔLE**

EDMS	3317020	Date de la mesure	03/07/2025 15:53
Job	3101080	N° de plan	134-75071
Client	GONZALEZ Sergio	Désignation	IFAST XBAND ASSY
Contrôleur	DEQUIDT Mike	Fournisseur	
Machine	ZEISS Prismo Ultra 12-18-10	N° de pièce	135-00882-002-2
Précision des mesures	1,2 µm + L/500mm	Valeurs rouges	● 203
Température	20°C ±1°C		

Commentaire

Nom du programme EDMS.3317020 - J3101080 - IAFST XBAND ASSY

Numero de serie

EDMS 3317020
 N° de plan 134-75071
 Désignation IFAST XBAND ASSY
 N° de pièce 135-00882-002-2
 Date/Heure 03/07/2025 15:53

Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
∅ Diamètre1(1)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(2)	80,0120	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0120	0,0100
∅ Diamètre1(3)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(4)	80,0112	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0112	0,0092
∅ Diamètre1(5)	80,0092	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0092	0,0072
∅ Diamètre1(6)	80,0113	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0113	0,0093
∅ Diamètre1(7)	80,0146	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0146	0,0126
∅ Diamètre1(8)	80,0125	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0125	0,0105
∅ Diamètre1(9)	80,0093	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0093	0,0073
∅ Diamètre1(10)	80,0100	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0100	0,0080
∅ Diamètre1(11)	80,0102	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0102	0,0082
∅ Diamètre1(12)	80,0123	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0123	0,0103
∅ Diamètre1(13)	80,0114	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0114	0,0094
∅ Diamètre1(14)	80,0116	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0116	0,0096
∅ Diamètre1(15)	80,0133	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0133	0,0113
∅ Diamètre1(16)	80,0143	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0143	0,0123
∅ Diamètre1(17)	80,0142	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0142	0,0122
∅ Diamètre1(18)	80,0158	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0158	0,0138
∅ Diamètre1(19)	80,0140	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0140	0,0120
∅ Diamètre1(20)	80,0118	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0118	0,0098
∅ Diamètre1(21)	80,0137	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0137	0,0117
∅ Diamètre1(22)	80,0154	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0154	0,0134
∅ Diamètre1(23)	80,0145	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0145	0,0125
∅ Diamètre1(24)	80,0136	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0136	0,0116
∅ Diamètre1(25)	80,0130	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0130	0,0110
∅ Diamètre1(26)	80,0118	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0118	0,0098
∅ Diamètre1(27)	80,0075	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0075	0,0055
∅ Diamètre1(28)	80,0089	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0089	0,0069
∅ Diamètre1(29)	80,0107	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0107	0,0087
∅ Diamètre1(30)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089

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Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-	
∅ Diamètre1(31)	80,0098	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0098		0,0078
∅ Diamètre1(32)	80,0124	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0124		0,0104
∅ Diamètre1(33)	80,0124	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0124		0,0104
∅ Diamètre1(34)	80,0129	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0129		0,0109
∅ Diamètre1(35)	80,0129	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0129		0,0109
∅ Diamètre1(36)	80,0128	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0128		0,0108
∅ Diamètre1(37)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109		0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(38)	80,0107	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0107		0,0087
∅ Diamètre1(39)	80,0110	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0110		0,0090
∅ Diamètre1(40)	80,0095	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0095		0,0075
∅ Diamètre1(41)	80,0135	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0135		0,0115
∅ Diamètre1(42)	80,0128	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0128		0,0108
∅ Diamètre1(43)	80,0133	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0133		0,0113
∅ Diamètre1(44)	80,0113	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0113		0,0093
∅ Diamètre1(45)	80,0128	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0128		0,0108
∅ Diamètre1(46)	80,0111	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0111		0,0091
∅ Diamètre1(47)	80,0131	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0131		0,0111
∅ Diamètre1(48)	80,0154	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0154		0,0134
∅ Diamètre1(49)	80,0121	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0121		0,0101
∅ Diamètre1(50)	80,0107	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0107		0,0087
∅ Diamètre1(51)	80,0127	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0127		0,0107
∅ Diamètre1(52)	80,0147	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0147		0,0127
∅ Diamètre1(53)	80,0176	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0176		0,0156
∅ Diamètre1(54)	80,0168	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0168		0,0148
∅ Diamètre1(55)	80,0126	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0126		0,0106
∅ Diamètre1(56)	80,0121	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0121		0,0101
∅ Diamètre1(57)	80,0087	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0087		0,0067
∅ Diamètre1(58)	80,0092	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0092		0,0072
∅ Diamètre1(59)	80,0100	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0100		0,0080
∅ Diamètre1(60)	80,0079	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0079		0,0059

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Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-	
∅ Diamètre1(61)	80,0087	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0087		0,0067
∅ Diamètre1(62)	80,0099	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0099		0,0079
∅ Diamètre1(63)	80,0074	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0074		0,0054
∅ Diamètre1(64)	80,0087	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0087		0,0067
∅ Diamètre1(65)	80,0089	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0089		0,0069
∅ Diamètre1(66)	80,0094	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0094		0,0074
∅ Diamètre1(67)	80,0129	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0129		0,0109
∅ Diamètre1(68)	80,0166	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0166		0,0146
∅ Diamètre1(69)	80,0158	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0158		0,0138
∅ Diamètre1(70)	80,0118	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0118		0,0098
∅ Diamètre1(71)	80,0096	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0096		0,0076
∅ Diamètre1(72)	80,0091	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0091		0,0071
∅ Diamètre1(73)	80,0088	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0088		0,0068
∅ Diamètre1(74)	80,0069	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0069		0,0049
∅ Diamètre1(75)	80,0078	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0078		0,0058
∅ Diamètre1(76)	80,0081	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0081		0,0061
∅ Diamètre1(77)	80,0097	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0097		0,0077
∅ Diamètre1(78)	80,0115	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0115		0,0095
∅ Diamètre1(79)	80,0130	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0130		0,0110
∅ Diamètre1(80)	80,0103	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0103		0,0083
∅ Diamètre1(81)	80,0075	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0075		0,0055
∅ Diamètre1(82)	80,0072	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0072		0,0052
∅ Diamètre1(83)	80,0098	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0098		0,0078
∅ Diamètre1(84)	80,0088	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0088		0,0068
∅ Diamètre1(85)	80,0073	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0073		0,0053
∅ Diamètre1(86)	80,0096	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0096		0,0076
∅ Diamètre1(87)	80,0124	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0124		0,0104
∅ Diamètre1(88)	80,0120	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0120		0,0100
∅ Diamètre1(89)	80,0103	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0103		0,0083
∅ Diamètre1(90)	80,0131	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0131		0,0111

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∅ Diamètre1(91)	80,0154	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0154	0,0134
∅ Diamètre1(92)	80,0161	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0161	0,0141
∅ Diamètre1(93)	80,0157	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0157	0,0137
∅ Diamètre1(94)	80,0128	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0128	0,0108
∅ Diamètre1(95)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(96)	80,0122	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0122	0,0102
∅ Diamètre1(97)	80,0140	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0140	0,0120
∅ Diamètre1(98)	80,0087	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0087	0,0067
∅ Diamètre1(99)	80,0070	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0070	0,0050
∅ Diamètre1(100)	80,0074	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0074	0,0054
∅ Diamètre1(101)	80,0066	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0066	0,0046
∅ Diamètre1(102)	80,0100	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0100	0,0080
⊕ Localisation1(1)	0,0302	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0302	
⊕ Localisation1(2)	0,0219	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0219	
⊕ Localisation1(3)	0,0647	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0647	0,0147
⊕ Localisation1(4)	0,0888	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0888	0,0388
⊕ Localisation1(5)	0,1152	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1152	0,0652
⊕ Localisation1(6)	0,1377	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1377	0,0877
⊕ Localisation1(7)	0,1589	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1589	0,1089
⊕ Localisation1(8)	0,1807	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1807	0,1307
⊕ Localisation1(9)	0,2010	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2010	0,1510
⊕ Localisation1(10)	0,2172	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2172	0,1672
⊕ Localisation1(11)	0,2351	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2351	0,1851
⊕ Localisation1(12)	0,2530	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2530	0,2030
⊕ Localisation1(13)	0,2692	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2692	0,2192
⊕ Localisation1(14)	0,2849	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2849	0,2349
⊕ Localisation1(15)	0,2971	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2971	0,2471
⊕ Localisation1(16)	0,3104	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3104	0,2604
⊕ Localisation1(17)	0,3235	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3235	0,2735
⊕ Localisation1(18)	0,3352	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3352	0,2852

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⊕ Localisation1(19)	0,3479	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3479	0,2979
⊕ Localisation1(20)	0,3572	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3572	0,3072
⊕ Localisation1(21)	0,3664	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3664	0,3164
⊕ Localisation1(22)	0,3752	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3752	0,3252
⊕ Localisation1(23)	0,3838	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3838	0,3338
⊕ Localisation1(24)	0,3906	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3906	0,3406
⊕ Localisation1(25)	0,3969	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3969	0,3469
⊕ Localisation1(26)	0,4028	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4028	0,3528
⊕ Localisation1(27)	0,4081	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4081	0,3581
⊕ Localisation1(28)	0,4111	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4111	0,3611
⊕ Localisation1(29)	0,4138	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4138	0,3638
⊕ Localisation1(30)	0,4171	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4171	0,3671
⊕ Localisation1(31)	0,4191	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4191	0,3691
⊕ Localisation1(32)	0,4201	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4201	0,3701
⊕ Localisation1(33)	0,4196	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4196	0,3696
⊕ Localisation1(34)	0,4187	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4187	0,3687
⊕ Localisation1(35)	0,4161	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4161	0,3661
⊕ Localisation1(36)	0,4147	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4147	0,3647
⊕ Localisation1(37)	0,4111	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4111	0,3611
⊕ Localisation1(38)	0,4087	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4087	0,3587
⊕ Localisation1(39)	0,4040	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4040	0,3540
⊕ Localisation1(40)	0,3997	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3997	0,3497
⊕ Localisation1(41)	0,3908	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3908	0,3408
⊕ Localisation1(42)	0,3843	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3843	0,3343
⊕ Localisation1(43)	0,3753	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3753	0,3253
⊕ Localisation1(44)	0,3667	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3667	0,3167
⊕ Localisation1(45)	0,3564	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3564	0,3064
⊕ Localisation1(46)	0,3460	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3460	0,2960
⊕ Localisation1(47)	0,3343	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3343	0,2843
⊕ Localisation1(48)	0,3193	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3193	0,2693

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⊕ Localisation1(49)	0,3065	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3065		0,2565
⊕ Localisation1(50)	0,2931	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2931		0,2431
⊕ Localisation1(51)	0,2779	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2779		0,2279
⊕ Localisation1(52)	0,2603	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2603		0,2103
⊕ Localisation1(53)	0,2428	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2428		0,1928
⊕ Localisation1(54)	0,2234	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2234		0,1734
⊕ Localisation1(55)	0,2048	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2048		0,1548
⊕ Localisation1(56)	0,1851	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1851		0,1351
⊕ Localisation1(57)	0,1657	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1657		0,1157
⊕ Localisation1(58)	0,1439	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1439		0,0939
⊕ Localisation1(59)	0,1215	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1215		0,0715
⊕ Localisation1(60)	0,0992	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0992		0,0492
⊕ Localisation1(61)	0,0765	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0765		0,0265
⊕ Localisation1(62)	0,0514	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0514		0,0014
⊕ Localisation1(63)	0,0259	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0259		
⊕ Localisation1(64)	0,0129	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0129		
⊕ Localisation1(65)	0,0391	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0391		
⊕ Localisation1(66)	0,0673	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0673		0,0173
⊕ Localisation1(67)	0,0970	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0970		0,0470
⊕ Localisation1(68)	0,1284	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1284		0,0784
⊕ Localisation1(69)	0,1563	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1563		0,1063
⊕ Localisation1(70)	0,1871	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1871		0,1371
⊕ Localisation1(71)	0,2188	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2188		0,1688
⊕ Localisation1(72)	0,2510	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2510		0,2010
⊕ Localisation1(73)	0,2833	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2833		0,2333
⊕ Localisation1(74)	0,3164	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3164		0,2664
⊕ Localisation1(75)	0,3512	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3512		0,3012
⊕ Localisation1(76)	0,3854	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3854		0,3354
⊕ Localisation1(77)	0,4227	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4227		0,3727
⊕ Localisation1(78)	0,4589	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4589		0,4089

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⊕ Localisation1(79)	0,4954	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4954	0,4454
⊕ Localisation1(80)	0,5319	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,5319	0,4819
⊕ Localisation1(81)	0,5722	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,5722	0,5222
⊕ Localisation1(82)	0,6098	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,6098	0,5598
⊕ Localisation1(83)	0,6495	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,6495	0,5995
⊕ Localisation1(84)	0,6894	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,6894	0,6394
⊕ Localisation1(85)	0,7329	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,7329	0,6829
⊕ Localisation1(86)	0,7754	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,7754	0,7254
⊕ Localisation1(87)	0,8185	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,8185	0,7685
⊕ Localisation1(88)	0,8604	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,8604	0,8104
⊕ Localisation1(89)	0,9037	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,9037	0,8537
⊕ Localisation1(90)	0,9489	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,9489	0,8989
⊕ Localisation1(91)	0,9957	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,9957	0,9457
⊕ Localisation1(92)	1,0416	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,0416	0,9916
⊕ Localisation1(93)	1,0865	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,0865	1,0365
⊕ Localisation1(94)	1,1334	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,1334	1,0834
⊕ Localisation1(95)	1,1809	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,1809	1,1309
⊕ Localisation1(96)	1,2272	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2272	1,1772
⊕ Localisation1(97)	1,2737	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2737	1,2237
⊕ Localisation1(98)	1,2993	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2993	1,2493
⊕ Localisation1(99)	1,3020	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,3020	1,2520
⊕ Localisation1(100)	1,2806	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2806	1,2306
⊕ Localisation1(101)	1,2585	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2585	1,2085
⊕ Localisation1(102)	1,2362	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2362	1,1862
— Rectitude axe cylindre	0,5177	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,5177	0,4177
— Rectitude Y-	0,1301	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,1301	0,0301
— Rectitude X-	0,5001	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,5001	0,4001
— Rectitude X+	0,4842	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,4842	0,3842
— Rectitude Y+	0,0350	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,0350	0,0350

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Nom

axe cylindre

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Nom

axe Y-

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